

Production of Objective Tourist Routes and Infrastructure of Historical Architectural Objects of the Bukhara Region

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Abstract

The article examines all existing historical monuments in the Bukhara region, comprehensive measures to diversify tourism in the national economy, accelerate regional development, create new jobs, increase income and living standards, increase the country's investment attractiveness as one of the proposals of strategic sectors for implementation.

Keywords: tourist areas, historical monuments, diversity, seven shrines of Pira, national economy, heritage sites,

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Introduction

The city of Bukhara and the Bukhara region for the further development and increase of the efficiency of the tourist potential, creation of more favorable conditions for acquaintance of tourists with the unique objects of historical, cultural and architectural heritage and ensuring the rapid development of modern tourist infrastructure in the region. , the development of a State program to expand the list and improve the quality of hotel and transport services (the Program for the accelerated development of the tourist potential of Bukhara and Bukhara region for 2017-2019) is a priority in this area.

It's time to introduce new economically promising and productive industries in the world for the development of the national economy of our country, which is now working on global integration.

Therefore, the development of tourism in Uzbekistan is a matter of national importance. The relevance of this issue lies in the fact that the international development of the tourism market has its own characteristics, and today it is necessary to know market relations in order to correctly identify the problems of tourism development.

Because, not knowing international tourism, it will be difficult to integrate into the world tourism community, cooperate and develop tourism in Uzbekistan at the international and local levels. One of the foundations for the development of international tourism, as well as national tourism, is the development of tourist routes and attracting tourists to these routes.

A well thought out, interestingly designed tourist route attracts many tourists. Therefore, there is a great demand for qualified specialists who can perfectly design tourist routes, and teaching this course is one of the most pressing issues in the development of tourism in Uzbekistan.

Research methods

Bukhara is one of the oldest cities in Central Asia and one of the largest and most famous trade centers on the Great Silk Road. The city is known all over the world for its rich and unique history, formed over millennia, which is closely related to the most important stages in the development of world civilization and made a huge contribution to the development of culture, education and development. spiritual and religious values.

In the Zoroastrian period Bukhara was known as Bukhara - "the center of science". During the Islamic period it was called "Bukhara Sharif" and was awarded the title "Ubbatil Islam". UNESCO World Heritage Site. On the land of Bukhara, such great scientists as Abu Nasr ibn Muhammad Farobi, Abu Ali ibn Sino, Abdullah Jafar Rudaki, Imam Bukhari Bahauddin Nashbandi, were the cradle of many world famous people. Bukhara is located on The Ark fortress, the Samanid mausoleum built in the 9th century AD, the architectural ensembles of Poi Kalon, Labi Pul and many other monumental architectural wonders built in the 9th century AD are the products of the Bukhara architectural school.

The Great Silk Road in Central Asia and is one of the most ancient cities of world culture and history, distinguished by its unique appearance, cultural heritage sites, and architectural monuments. Bukhara is a huge museum under the sky, a living book. Built in many architectural styles by many generations of our distant and great ancestors. The city of Bukhara is the pride of our people. The integral architectural ensembles created over two and a half thousand years are the fruit of the Bukhara architectural school. The architectural history of Bukhara continues from west to east.

The history of eastern monuments begins in the west with the cultural heritage site Ark and the mausoleum of Ismail Somoni, Poya Kalon with an architectural ensemble, trade rastas - "wonderful" and "tims", the architectural ensemble Lyabi Khovuz and others. The architectural ensembles of Bukhara have been formed over hundreds of years, millennia and are linked by a single plan-spatial composition.

Results

The Bukhara Architectural School developed the traditions of the advanced building culture of the XV-XVII centuries. Creative architects, knowledgeable builders and engineers, master craftsmen have done a lot of urban planning work. The Bukhara School of Architecture, while the only leading force in Central Asia, also played an important role in the development of schools of architecture in other regions. The Bukhara architectural school of the late period was further developed thanks to such great architects of the twentieth century as the master Shirin Murodov.

The fact that the city of Bukhara has been declared a historical and architectural museum-reserve testifies to the importance of important architectural structures. In Bukhara, there are not only ancient mosques, madrasahs and mausoleums, but also a number of residential buildings and other objects built according to old plans. There are 660 cultural heritage sites in Bukhara region, in which 997 architectural monuments are registered. In particular, there are 264 cultural heritage sites in Bukhara, including more than 350 architectural monuments. Of the 264 objects listed above, 183 are public and 81 are residential. There are more than 30 architectural monuments at the Bahauddin Naqshbandi cultural heritage site alone.

Bukhara is located in the middle of the mainland, far from the oceans, at an altitude of 226 m above sea level. There will be very little precipitation. The climate is harsh and dry, with very hot summers. Although the average temperature in July is above 30 ° C, there are days when summer temperatures exceed 45 ° C.

Results and reviews: The analysis of tourism statistics was as follows:

Expenditures on domestic tourism in 2019 by product, category of visitors and type of travel (in millions of soums)

Table 1

Typical travel products	Tourists (visitors for a day or more)	Tourists (one-day visitors)	Visitors
A. Consumer goods	8 930 081,5	10 744 259,1	19 674 340,6
1. Typical travel products	6 662 713,6	3 995 730,9	10 658 444,5
2. Accommodation services for visitors	1 122 615,2	X	1 122 615,2
3. Catering services	687 202,3	1 830 255,0	2 517 457,3
4. Railway passenger transport services	370 992,1	26 150,0	397 142,1
5. Land passenger transport services	1 828 050,3	1 864 675,9	3 692 726,1
6. Air passenger services	2 194 639,3		2 194 639,3
7. Travel agency and other	283 100,0	750,0	283 850,0

booking services			
8. Services in the field of culture	96 614,4	89 500,0	186 114,4
9. Services in the field of sports and leisure	79 500,0	184 400,0	263 900,0
2. Other consumer goods	2 267 367,9	6 748 528,2	9 015 896,1
B. Other products	1 219 989,2	1 373 229,4	2 593 218,5
Total	10 150 070,6	12 117 488,4	22 267 559,1

Based on the above data, we have highlighted the following. The volume of expenses on domestic tourism by categories of visitors and types of travel as of 2019 amounted to 10,150,070.6 million soums for tourists (visitors per day or more), 12,117,488.4 million soums for tourists (one-day visitors). UZS, 22,267,559.1 million soums for visitors. Including the most expensive products include the usual travel products. Their share in the total number was 74.6% for tourists (visitors for a day or more), 37.1% for tourists (one-day visitors) and 54.2% for visitors.

According to the data, the number of visitors to our country was 16.8% in three directions, 17-20% - on land passenger transport, 24-25% - on air traffic.

The possibilities of developing the following tourist services in our country were studied.

1. Rural tourism
2. Tourism in Jailoo
3. Gastronomic tourism.
4. Festival tourism.
5. Pilgrimage tourism.
6. Medical tourism
7. Shopping tourism.
8. Ecotourism

In order to deepen the study of cultural heritage sites, architectural monuments and continue the traditions of the local architectural and construction school, special attention was paid to the training of architects with higher education in Bukhara. Accordingly, since 2008, the Bukhara Technological Institute has decided to recruit architects, as well as architects who are already undergoing training.

Experts note that tourism is a promising branch of the modern economy. While the development of other industries constantly requires raw materials, labor, capital and many other resources, for tourism it is enough to have a fluffy infrastructure that meets modern requirements: the example of the fruit tree will be beneficial for many years. The President pays special attention to this aspect in large-scale reforms aimed at ensuring the development of our country and the well-being of our people. A number of documents are being adopted on a comprehensive reform of the industry. According to them, the country creates favorable conditions for the tourism industry, removes barriers to the development of the industry, simplifies visa and registration procedures for foreigners, and customs control.

For young people who have seen her current beauty, it looks like a fairy tale. What is important, today the complex is flourishing as never before, all conditions for visitors have been created here, a group of tourists from Malaysia came to the complex. They said that they were very glad that Khoja Baba had visited the Samoan sanctuary.

“Many scientists born in Uzbekistan have left a deep mark on the Islamic world,” says one of the tourists, Bin Hasan Jamalidin. - You can be proud of such ancestors. The Naqshbandi sect is widespread in our country. That is why many of our compatriots want to visit the Seven Feasts and get acquainted with the rich culture of their people.

It should be noted that the visa regime has been canceled for Malaysian citizens visiting Uzbekistan for tourist purposes for a period not exceeding 30 days. We are very pleased with this. Also, construction and repair work is in full swing at the shrine of Khoja Muhammad Arif Revgari in the Shafirkan region. On an area of about five hectares, a garden, a flower garden, a hotel, a minaret, a mosque, a toilet and a museum of various fruit and ornamental trees are being built.

Each object here has been restored in all respects in a way convenient for visitors, based on national and modern architectural traditions. It can also be seen that attention is paid to symbolism in creativity. For example, the pool was dug in the shape of a crescent moon. Workers say the flowers are also planted in a crescent shape in early spring. This sign of happiness is a sign that Camille was revered as "Mojitobon" or "moon face".

The masters decorating the walls of the mosque do not stop. “This is our visit today and our prayer,” he said. We hope for blessings and blessings from God, ”they said. Each ganch is approached with special kindness and passion. After all, every lettering and pattern has a deep expression and content that gives people spiritual strength and guides them on the right path.

“Muhammad Arif Revgari was a blessed man, whose face shone with light, and his body smelled of musk,” says one of the craftsmen, a labor veteran Botir Bobomurodov. - His steps must be great in accordance with his status. We are working on this with our team. The master emphasized that the responsibility for the restoration of ancient monuments is great. They embody the spirit and thoughts of our ancestors. Therefore, this work requires not only deep knowledge and potential, but also high spiritual strength.

“Let me point out one thing,” he said. “The number of craftsmen who are able to restore the beauty of centuries-old buildings and the essence of each pattern in them is decreasing over the years. We are the same age. Sometimes he said: “I learned how to repair ancient monuments from my father, master Achil Bobomurodov.

Who am I leaving this legacy to today? »Indeed, in our country, which is the hearth of an ancient civilization, there are thousands of monuments. Wouldn't they need to be repaired again? If this work is entrusted to an experienced builder, the priceless examples of architecture will lose their charm. Time and money are wasted. If there is an opportunity to invite talented and loving youth, if necessary, travel around the country, find them and make them students.

If a special school for restorers opened, there would be light. We had no hope. The world famous British newspaper “The Independent” recently published an article about the visit of the traveling journalist Claire Wood to Uzbekistan. In his speech, the author names eight reasons for visiting Uzbekistan and emphasizes that everyone should see, enjoy and admire the intricate domed monuments of our country, the sophisticated and elegant ceramic tiles used in their decoration.

Everyone who looks at the majestic dome of the mausoleum of Sayyid Amir Kulol in the Kagan region will once again be convinced of the veracity of the confessions on this score. At the same time, he is glad that existing facilities are being renovated today and new facilities are being built in the complex for the convenience of visitors.

"We always pay attention to the Piri Kamil mausoleum, built on the basis of national architectural traditions, the columns and arches of the mosque, created using unique wood carvings, doors and frames that do not lose their charm," says Kagan's youth policy. Deputy for Social Development and Spiritual and Educational Work Zubaidullo Shakhripov. - Because pilgrims, first of all, seek peace, purity, prosperity.

Therefore, in the process of improving the complex, flower beds and green lawns are created. Along with local trees, valuable seedlings brought from abroad are also planted. During the construction and renovation of buildings and structures, attention is paid to the combination of nationalism and modernity.

Another bright place in the area is the shrine of Hazrat Bahauddin in the village of Kasri Orifon. On the way from the Bukhara international airport to this village, on the instructions of the President, the message "Welcome to the land of Bahauddin Naqshband! Welcome to the homeland of Bahauddin Naqshband! »Your eyes will be drawn to the banner and your heart will be drawn more clearly. Such banners, information about the shrine and its owner, pointers helping to find the right address are intended only for visitors.

The growing population of Muslim countries, as well as the growing Muslim diaspora in developed countries, means that this factor needs to be addressed. The growing population of Muslim countries, as well as the growth of the Muslim diaspora in developed countries, means that this factor needs to be addressed. In this regard, British Muslims are delighted to hear about new direct flights from Istanbul to Bukhara and Samarkand. It is clear that Central Asia, in particular Uzbekistan, will benefit from an individual approach to this area of tourism.

Visiting unusual places and adventures in these places is just as important as visiting tourist attractions. Perhaps this trend seems interesting also because people tend to experience more adrenaline and unusual emotions. Several pilgrim tourism initiatives show that there is a lot of speculation in this regard. In this regard, the Bukhara Declaration on Pilgrimage Tourism was adopted within the framework of the first International Forum of Pilgrimage Tourism on Friday, February 22, 2019 (17 Jumodus, 1440 AH), Bukhara, Republic of Uzbekistan.

The organizers of the Tashkent Law Spring International Legal Forum (Forum) have developed a cultural program in interesting cities of Uzbekistan, including Bukhara. For an additional fee of \$ 200, participants will be able to visit the city of Bukhara and see historical and cultural monuments included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. The cost of the tourist package includes tickets Tashkent-Bukhara and there and back, from the station to the hotel and from the hotel to the station, one-day hotel accommodation, breakfast, 2 lunches and 1 dinner, a concert program. as monuments of history and culture and attractions.

Conclusion

Taking into account the above, we have come to the following conclusion. In this process, we would like to make the following suggestions.

1. Radical modernization of the infrastructure of the "Seven Shrines of the Pir" in the Bukhara region.
2. Development of a procedure for the reconstruction of roads leading to shrines in connection with the need for repair.
3. Identify the sources of unknown saints and prophets in our country and introduce innovations in pilgrim tourism.
4. Identify women's shrines characteristic of the same region, conduct archaeological research and include them in the list of tourist sites.

5. To radically reconstruct women's mausoleums and madrasahs and bring them in line with world tourism standards in order to strengthen the image of our country as a safe place for travel and recreation.
6. Provision of tax and customs privileges to tourist sites for pilgrim tourism.
7. Allow entrepreneurs to reduce VAT by providing access to free wireless Internet (Wi-Fi).
8. Implementation of a virtual travel system for pilgrim tourism.

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